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TOBACCO SMOKING AS A FACTOR AFFECTING THE ENVIRONMENT AND HUMAN HEALTH

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Annotation: The article focuses on the problem of tobacco smoking and its impact on the environment and humans. In the course of the research, search, analytical, comparative and evaluation methods were used. It has been established that tobacco smoking by the strength of its negative impact on the human body and the environment refers to extreme environmental factors. According to the form of exposure, tobacco smoking can be attributed to mutagenic and carcinogenic environmental factors. Smoking is a risk factor for many health disorders, and is also a polluting factor of the internal environment of the body and the environment

Keywords: human health, internal environment of the body, environment, tobacco, smoking, environmental factor

Relevance. Tobacco consumption and production has a negative impact on the environment. Smoking can be defined as an environmental factor, the importance of which is constantly increasing in the modern world.

Tobacco contained in a cigarette is grown under special conditions and undergoes a complex manufacturing process, which negatively affects the state of the environment. The first factor in the manufacture of tobacco is deforestation. Tobacco cultivation requires large areas of fertile land, as well as considerable amounts of wood for the construction of dryers and the actual drying of tobacco.

But speaking of nature, do not forget that, first of all, people are under the harmful influence of tobacco products. The process of smoking has a thousand-year history, starting from the representatives of the Maya Indians, where tobacco had a ritual significance, ending with our days, where the meaning of smoking remains in question [1]. At the same time, knowing about the dangers of smoking, the number of smokers around the world is growing [2]. Smoking is one of the most urgent problems of environmental medicine and society.

The purpose of the study. To focus attention on the problem of tobacco smoking and its impact on the environment and humans.

Materials and methods of research. Search, analytical, comparative and evaluative. The materials were scientific data presented in Internet sources and on paper [1-6].

The results of the study and their discussion. As a result of data analysis, on average about 15 billion cigarettes are smoked worldwide per day, as a result of which [2] pollutants enter the atmosphere. Based on the study of data from the Ministry of Statistics and Analysis of the Republic of Belarus, 54.4 % of men smoke. At the age of 30-39 years, the number of smokers is 64.8 % for men and 14.9 % for women. At the age of 14-17, 34.2 % of smokers are smokers. 73 % of heavy smokers tried smoking before the age of 17, that is, while still in school.

As a result of the analysis of the data obtained, tobacco kills 5 million people worldwide every year (11 thousand people every day). In Belarus, about 15.5 thousand people die annually from smoking-related diseases. In 2020, tobacco became the leading cause of death of 10 million people worldwide [3].

Smoked cigarettes, cigarette packages and other tobacco products form garbage. Cigarette filters decompose within 5-7 years. Cigarette butts pose a threat to animals and plants. Toxic substances are released from cigarette butts, which causes inflammation of the digestive system of animals, as a result, intestinal obstruction develops, and the result is death [1].

In a number of countries, due to the low ecological culture of the population and the lack of harsh penalties, cigarette butts, in most cases, do not end up in landfills for burial, but remain on the land of settlements and forest territories. Decomposing, cigarette butts poison the soil with chemicals that are part of them (during the analysis, it was found that about 7360 different compounds are present in cigarettes, 70 of which have a carcinogenic effect on the human body) [4].

Unopened cigarettes, falling on vegetation, are a negative factor in the risk of fires. The maximum temperature of a smoldering cigarette varies between 300-420 C with a smoldering duration of 4-8 minutes. A cigarette can smolder for about 30 minutes, its temperature at this time is 310-320 C [5]. Before going out, a cigarette can cause the material on which it was thrown to decay. As a result, a new source of decay in 1-4 hours can cause a fire. For example, pine shingles ignite after 60-80 minutes, boards – after 180-210 minutes. The ignition of the paper may occur in an hour.

Forest fires are currently an urgent environmental problem [6]. They are the main cause of the death of forests in large areas. More than 880 forest fires are observed in Belarus every year. At the same time, the culprit of fires is a person. It is worth noting that in second place for the reasons of forest fire are the consequences of smoking. Thus, a cigarette thrown in the forest can cause the death of an entire ecosystem, a reduction in the number of certain species, and in some cases a decrease in the biological diversity of rare plant and animal species listed in the Red Book. As a result of the fire, birds and their nests, small mammals, invertebrates and microorganisms die. That is why smoking and its negative consequences are a factor that changes the environment and its individual structures.

Conclusions. Thus, tobacco smoking by the strength of its negative impact on the human body and the environment refers to extreme environmental factors. According to the form of exposure, tobacco smoking can be attributed to mutagenic and carcinogenic environmental factors. Based on the above, we can conclude that in the world: a large number of cigarettes are smoked, a huge number of tobacco consumers, smoking is a risk factor for many health disorders, including lung cancer, which occupies the 1st place in the structure of oncopathologies in the male population, tobacco products are a polluting factor of the internal environment of the body and the environment, and cigarettes are a source of fires.

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